

Psychological Characteristics of the New Generation of Students

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the psychological characteristics of the new generation of students (generation Z). The paper analyzes the impact of digital technologies on the style of thinking, perception of information and communication, changes in the system of values and motivation, as well as new trends in the style of learning and communication.

The article identifies the key psychological features of Generation Z, such as high digital alliteration, pragmatism, individualism, openness to new experiences, the desire for active and interactive learning, as well as the predominant use of online communication.

Keywords: generation Z, psychological characteristics, digital technologies, education, motivation, values, communication, adaptation, modern society, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork.

INTRODUCTION

The modern world is changing rapidly, and this is reflected in all spheres of life, including education. The new generation of students, who grew up in the era of digital technologies and globalization, has unique psychological characteristics that must be taken into account in the process of education and upbringing.

The relevance of the study of the psychological characteristics of the new generation of students is due to a number of factors. Firstly, digital technologies are playing an increasingly important role in their lives, shaping the way they think, perceive information and communicate. Secondly, changes in the system of values and motivation require a rethink of traditional pedagogical approaches. Thirdly, understanding the psychological characteristics of the new generation is necessary to create and adapt educational programs that meet their needs and contribute to their successful development.

PURPOSE OF WORK

To study the psychological characteristics of a new generation of students and determine their impact on the learning and upbringing process.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- Analyze the literature on the topic of psychological characteristics of the new generation of students.
- Identify the key psychological characteristics of the new generation of students.

- To determine the influence of the psychological characteristics of the new generation on the learning and upbringing process.
- Develop recommendations for adapting the educational system to changing conditions.

METHODS

To achieve the purpose of the study, methods such as the study and review of literature, theoretical data analysis were used.

DISCUSSION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

In recent decades, there has been a significant change in the psychology and behavior of students, which is associated with both technological advances and changes in the social and cultural context. The new generation of students, often referred to as "Generation Z" or "Generation alpha", demonstrates unique psychological characteristics that require special attention from educators and psychologists.

The issues of psychological characteristics of the new generation of students, known as Generation Z (people born from about the mid-1990s to the early 2010s), have attracted the attention of many researchers in the field of psychology, education and sociology. Including:

1. Jean M. Twenge is an American psychologist known for her research on Generation Z and their distinctive features. She is the author of the book "iGen", which examines the impact of technology on young people.
2. David Epstein is the author of the book "Range: Why Generalists Triumph in a Specialized World", in which he discusses the features of education and training of the new generation.
3. The Pew Research Center is an organization that conducts extensive research on various social issues, including the behavior and values of Generation Z.
4. Katherine L. Cohen is an educational researcher and author of several articles on the characteristics of Generation Z students.
5. Corey Seemiller is the co-author of the book "Generation Z Goes to College", which examines the unique characteristics of students of this generation.
6. Tamara E. Smith – investigated the impact of technology on the learning and socialization of Generation Z students.

Scientific research and literature analysis have shown that one of the striking features of the new generation is a high degree of digital literacy. Students are introduced to technology from an early age, which forms their habit of receiving information through the Internet and social networks. This leads to a change in learning styles: modern students prefer interactive and visual methods, and traditional lectures are often perceived as outdated. It is important to note that such dependence on technology can affect the level of concentration and the ability to deeply analyze information.

In addition, the new generation is characterized by a high degree of social responsibility and involvement in global problems. Students are actively involved in social movements such as the fight against climate change or the protection of human rights. This indicates that they have developed empathy and a desire to influence the world around them. However, it should be borne in mind that constant interaction with negative news can cause stress and anxiety.

Another key feature of the new generation is the desire for individualization and self-expression. Students are looking for opportunities to realize their interests and hobbies through a variety of learning formats — from project activities to online courses. This suggests the need to introduce flexible educational approaches that would take into account

the individual preferences of each student.

However, along with the positive aspects, challenges arise. Difficulties in interpersonal communication sometimes lead to social isolation; many students prefer communication in virtual space to real interaction. This highlights the importance of developing social skills among young people through the organization of group projects and activities.

RESULTS

Generation Z, who grew up in the digital age, has a high digital literacy, adapts easily to new gadgets and interfaces, and has developed information retrieval and multitasking skills. However, dependence on digital technologies can lead to a decrease in attention, concentration and critical thinking.

Changes in the value system of generation Z are characterized by pragmatism, individualism, the desire for self-realization, freedom of choice and quick results. They value practical knowledge and skills, and are open to new experiences and diversity.

New trends in the learning style reflect the desire of Generation Z for an active and interactive learning process, independent search for information and practical application of knowledge. Traditional methods of lectures and passive learning of the material may be ineffective for them.

Generation Z actively uses online communication, prefers short and concise messages, uses social networks and messengers as the main communication channel.

The results of the study confirm the need to adapt the educational system to the changing conditions and psychological characteristics of the new generation.

It is necessary to introduce innovative teaching methods and technologies, create an interactive and motivating atmosphere, develop students' critical thinking, creativity and teamwork skills.

CONCLUSION

Further research should be aimed at a deeper study of the psychological characteristics of generation Z in different areas of life and education, as well as the development of new pedagogical concepts and techniques that take into account modern realities.

The study revealed a number of key features of the new generation that require rethinking traditional approaches to education and upbringing. In order to effectively adapt the educational system to the changing conditions and psychological characteristics of the new generation of students, it is **recommended**:

1. Introduction of innovative teaching methods:

- ✓ *Active learning*: the use of project activities, case studies, game technologies, simulations and other interactive teaching methods that allow students to actively participate in the learning process and apply knowledge in practice.
- ✓ *A differentiated approach*: taking into account the individual characteristics of students, their interests and the pace of learning. Development of individual educational trajectories.
- ✓ *Problem-based learning*: setting up problem situations that stimulate critical thinking, creativity, and the search for solutions.

2. The use of digital technologies:

- ✓ *Creation of online platforms and resources*: development of online courses, interactive textbooks, virtual laboratories and other digital resources corresponding to the digital competencies of the new generation.

- ✓ *Application of mobile applications:* The use of mobile applications for learning, testing and knowledge control, which allows students to learn anytime and anywhere.
- ✓ *Development of digital competencies:* teaching students skills in working with digital tools, critical assessment of information and digital hygiene.

3. Formation of key competencies:

- ✓ *Development of critical thinking:* stimulating the analysis of information, identifying false facts, and formulating one's own position.
- ✓ *Increasing creativity:* creating conditions for creative thinking, taking initiative and implementing your own ideas.
- ✓ *Development of teamwork:* organization of project activities, group assignments and cooperation between students.

4. Creating a motivating atmosphere:

- ✓ *Positive interaction:* creating an atmosphere of respect, trust and support between teacher and student, encouraging independence and initiative.
- ✓ *Practical orientation:* linking learning with real life, demonstrating the practical application of knowledge and skills.
- ✓ *Individual approach:* taking into account the individual characteristics of students, their interests and motivation.

5. Continuous professional development of teachers:

- ✓ *Training in new methods and technologies:* teachers must constantly improve their knowledge and skills, master modern teaching methods and technologies, taking into account the characteristics of the new generation.
- ✓ *Exchange of experience:* creation of platforms for the exchange of experience between teachers, organization of conferences, seminars and master classes on modern teaching methods.

The implementation of these recommendations will make it possible to adapt the educational system to the changing conditions and psychological characteristics of a new generation of students, which will contribute to their successful development and preparation for life in the modern world.

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